

Quantum physics and quantum logic suggest that statements about future events can be made in the form of probabilistic judgments. This is consistent with Weizsäcker's assertion that the past can be interpreted in terms of the actually factual, and the future in the category of possibility.

Let us note that the use of the apparatus of logic by Weizsäcker is not accidental; he is looking for the basis of a physical theory and lays the logic of temporary statements at the basis of the theory. In philosophical terms, this is the postulation of ontology within one's scientific program.

Mathematical and logical foundations turn out to be the foundation for the theoretical constructions of science. The secondary nature of the space-time structure in the construction of a physical theory indicates the primacy of ideal structures. The material (that which exists in space and time) comes from the ideal (non-spatial and timeless layer).

Here we are talking about a "different" mode of reality that constitutes the observed.

In schematic form, the result is represented by the Ontological Triangle. Inside the triangle there are all kinds of material objects, from elementary particles to Metagalaxies, and the boundaries of the material type of existence are three types of immaterial existence: space, time and ideal.

Material, ideal, temporal and spatial types of existence, which fit schematically into a triangle.

Ontology, among other problems, deals with the search for the initial ultimate foundations of all being. In this sense, material existence is not initial, since it stems from prematerial spatial and temporal existence. But space and time can already claim to be the original types of existence that are not reducible to something else.

Space doesn't need time, and time doesn't need space to exist. But space exists as space, and time exists as time. Unlike them, ideal being does not need either space or time.

In terms of independence from space and time, it turns out to be more fundamental than space and time itself. Therefore, the ideal lies at the base of the ontological triangle, and space and time form the remaining two symmetrical sides.

In further analysis of the complex truth value, von Weizsäcker points to another side of it, which is clarified as a result of the introduction of additional alternatives.

A pair of numbers (u, v) can be considered as a two-component complex vector. Let two statements A_1 and A_2 be given, forming the initial alternative: A_1 – "The particle passed through the first slit" A_2 – "The particle passed through the second slit". The truth vector is $(1,0)$ when A_1 is true, and $(0,1)$ when A_2 is true.

Weizsäcker further states that each vector (u, v) normalized by the above relation is associated with a statement that is true if the statements representing a given alternative have corresponding truth values u, v . Every statement defined by the vector (u, v) that is not itself A_1 and A_2 is considered to be complementary to A_1 and A_2 .

Thus, having arrived at many-valued logic through the introduction of complex truth values, von Weizsäcker formulates in the language of logic a certain interpretation of complementarity. However, Weizsäcker does not even extend his semantic construction to a matrix one; it makes no attempt at syntactic description. This indicates that the transition from the semantic level to the syntactic level is at least non-trivial.

And the fact that Weizsäcker does not construct his system in the form of a calculus makes the question of the adequacy of his proposed interpretation of complementarity with the actual state of affairs in quantum theory unclear. The ur-alternative has a direct reflection in logic.

In addition to 0 and 1, a complex number can also be used as the truth value of an elementary statement: It seems possible to answer the second question, which raised by von Weizsäcker: what simple alternatives are there in reality? As such simple alternatives, pairs of statements about simultaneously observable quantities can be taken.

More than 80 years have passed since the beginning of research into quantum logic by G. Birkhoff and J. von Neumann. Weizsäcker stood almost at the very beginning of discussions about the relationship between classical logic and the logic of quantum mechanics. The answer to the question whether the laws of classical logic are violated in the microworld was one of the key ones.

This question is at the intersection of physics, mathematics and logic, because the understanding of quantum phenomena is carried out from different sides. Weizsäcker in general applies the principle of complementarity to quantum logic, which was negatively perceived by N. Bohr: "...attest to at least the works of N. Bohr himself, who never tired of emphasizing the principle of complementarity in understanding the world.

We can distinguish ontological unity and epistemological unity; physical theory includes both characteristics. As a rule, they are closely interrelated. Epistemic unity applies to epistemic attitudes or goals such as explanation. Methodological connections and formal (logical, mathematical, etc.) models may belong to this type.

Weizsäcker, by appealing to Kant, defines the epistemological basis of his program, the conditions for the possibility of experience are space and time. Modern quantum experiments reveal the fundamental importance of time.

Ontological unity is broadly understood as the relationship between conceptual elements; in some cases these are entities, facts, properties or relations, and models of description will focus on the metaphysical aspects of unifying connections, such as holism. The path to ontology in his Weizsäcker program sees through logic.

The scientist adheres to the methodology of philosophical epistemological analysis, choosing experience as the object on which the theoretical theory should be built. part of physics. From Weizsäcker's point of view, experience is formed as data obtained in the past regarding the future: Physics is based on experience; and experience means learning lessons for the future from the past.

Consequently, the first place among the conditions for the possibility of experience comes to the structure of time itself in its modes of present, future and past.

And initially, in the very structure of the concept “experience” there is a fundamental difference between the past and the future or a specific structure of time. If you follow the strict definition, then nothing in the world can return, which means that all events are irreversible. In experience, the past is described in terms of facts - in order to draw conclusions about possibilities of the future.

Thus, Weizsäcker defines time as a fundamental phenomenon for any knowledge that a subject possesses in relation to reality. Time, ultimately, constitutes the objectivity of knowledge in physics. In "The Construction of Physics" Weizsäcker provides a number of evidence regarding the inextricable and fundamental role of the structure of time.

The importance of this element for the creation of physical laws with detailed conceptual elaboration, as well as for deepening the understanding of such physical concepts, is highlighted. as probability, causality, irreversibility, entropy, and thereby the evolution of matter.

With the help of physical laws, predictions are formulated that relate to the results of measurements in the future. For example, quantum theory demonstrates to the observer that data obtained in an experiment are always subject to statistical dispersion.

It is important to note that all possible predictions regarding future results that do not currently exist will remain strictly unconfirmed until such data is available. It is this fact that determines the characteristics of such forecasts as “possible” (but definitely neither true nor false).

Weizsäcker says that classical logic is a structural unit within the broad term “logic of temporal statements,” where a logical judgment about “statements about the future” will quite rightly have strong differences from “what has happened.”

Weizsäcker's main idea is that a logical structure built on temporary statements will be fundamental to both classical logic and quantum theory. Moreover, such a structure must be inextricably linked with probability: The central concept of quantum theory, as it is usually formulated, must be the concept of probability.

In physics, probability has predictive value. This last characteristic is deeply intertwined with experience. This is argued by the fact that confirmation during observation or rejection of a theoretical postulate cannot be reliably carried out, but it can be done with a high or low degree of probability. One of Weizsäcker's key thoughts is the thesis that the factuality of the past does not correlate with the modality of probability, due to the unambiguous documentation of such a phenomenon.

All this is a strong argument in favor of understanding probabilistic judgments only in a plane related to the future. This single thought alone leads us to the irreversibility of natural processes, as formulated in the second fundamental law of thermodynamics.

This seems to be the only possible way, which harmoniously links the formalism of mathematical transformations of physics and the “semantics” of natural phenomena. It becomes obvious that reversibility cannot be described using mathematics alone. The closely intertwined physical concepts, as well as their dependence on the structure of time, which Weizsäcker discusses, are organically included in the construction of physics.

Weizsäcker sets himself the task of substantiating the unity of nature based on quantum theory. He presented the initial algorithms for realizing his plans in an earlier book, “The Unity of Nature.”

"Building Physics" sets out the results of large-scale research that constitute a system of relationships between theoretical classical physics, chemistry, thermodynamics, relativity and quantum theory, and together this provides the basis for the reconstruction of quantum theory.

At the heart of Weizsäcker's "Construction of Physics" is the hypothesis that quantum theory can be formulated as a single fundamental theory and that "all known physics today" can be reduced to it. This is formulated as a “revolution in chronological sequence of arguments” leading to the formation of quantum theory. This is quite logical, since it is preceded by early classical theories.

In addition to this, Niels Bohr's thesis about the principle of complementarity between classical theories and modern quantum theory is based precisely on historical chronology. Based on this, Weizsäcker's intention was to reconstruct only quantum theory without taking into account previous theories on the basis of "clarified" postulates looks like a radical step. The reconstruction itself consists of two components.

On the one hand, this is the existence of distinguishable empirically solvable alternatives, on the other, “indeterminism.” A total of four reconstruction methods are considered, which differ from each other in their level of abstraction. Weizsäcker's main conclusion is that quantum theory helps to isolate a part from a whole based on a process of measurement, resulting in a final, complete object.

However, a contradiction arises in the process, such as the fact that the initial formulation of the question in front of the measuring device simultaneously generates several objects endowed with incommensurable properties. Which of the probable properties is realized depends on the type of equipment. This means that the objectification of reality essentially consists in solving alternatives, and objects are nothing more than empirically solved alternatives.

They indicate final knowledge about material structures, the form of the phenomenon of which is determined only by the researcher and only in the process of the research itself. The most problematic question of quantum theory is to what extent, during objectification, the separation of a part from the whole can be carried out - in the abstract formulation: to what extent alternatives can be separated from each other. The existence of limiting conditions is evidenced by the uncertainty principle formulated by Werner Heisenberg.

Weizsäcker suggests that the construction of quantum theory is possible on the concept of an alternative, while only the minimally logically possible binary alternative should be taken into account, which is a “yes” or “no” decision.

According to Weizsäcker's concept, the methodology for solving “primary alternatives” will be a source of knowledge about the objective universe. This is the so-called “hypothesis of radical atomism”, which can be compared exclusively with the concept of information as such.

Weizsäcker uses the “theory of original alternatives”, with the help of which he tries to build a unified system from the theory of relativity, quantum electrodynamics and particle physics (so that one theory is derived from the other).

In Weizsäcker's approach to the interpretation of quantum theory. The Copenhagen interpretation indicates that the clarity of a picture of a physical object is characterized by its accessibility to the observer. The reduction of the wave function occurs in the consciousness of the observer and does not represent an objective process, therefore the apparatus of quantum mechanics can be applied to the spiritual sphere.

Answering the question about the essence of substance as such, where there is a large-scale mutual intertwining of man and nature, object and subject, consciousness and matter, Weizsäcker formulates the concept of “form”, the numerical measure of which is “information”.

In Weizsäcker, he examines the issues of “physics beyond quantum theory” and “human knowledge beyond physics” step by step. The answers to the questions presented are given uncharacteristically briefly; Weizsäcker provides a specific philosophical interpretation only in the book “Time and Knowledge.”

An analysis of the philosophical judgments presented there indicates an increased degree of reflection. The whole is not recorded in the final answers. With this, Weizsäcker sets the intention for continued philosophizing . Weizsäcker pays special attention to the structure of time, realized in three modes. The present, Weizsäcker emphasizes, is not fully taken into account in classical physics; the moment “now” is assigned a subjective meaning. The future appears in modal categories of the possible, and we can have documented facts about the past.

The structure of time with three modes appears as a condition for the possibility of experience, but does not include the metaphysical dimension of eternity, the problem of which Weizsäcker understood well: “In relation to the eternal for time, we are forced to deviate from Aristotle and from all classical metaphysics.

At this point metaphysics contains an unsolved problem, which appears when we try to insert a modern view of time into metaphysics. For Parmenides, who makes the leap into the eternal present, the world of becoming and passing is “doxa,” which Fich quite appropriately translates as “appearance.”

But how does he come to this phenomenon? Where in the existing is that which gives rise to time and phenomenon? Plato explains time as aeonic, according to number, an advancing reflection of the eon frozen in the individual. Aeon means in Greek a meaningful time space, such as a season or a time of life. It is traditionally translated as eternity; then time is an eternal reflection of eternity.”

The structure of thermodynamics, quantum mechanics, and probability theory is revealed to him as fundamental differences between the past, present and future. Weizsäcker first criticizes Einstein's view of time. He perceived temporality subjectively, as an “illusion.”

One can also draw a fundamental difference between the views of Einstein and Weizsäcker. For Einstein, the laws of nature are factual in nature, but for Weizsäcker they are possible, because the laws of nature determine the possibility (probability) that is realized.

Time, on the one hand, in the spirit of Greek metaphysics, is the eternal present; on the other hand, in physics it is embodied in the picture of space-time, where space is complemented by a time dimension. Weizsäcker shows the possibilities of his understanding of time using the example of the interpretation of classical philosophical texts, namely the theory reality-possibility-movement of Aristotle.

In our language, possibility is a feature of the future, reality refers to the present. Factuality is documented reality. In this vein, one can even express it as follows: movement is the present of the future.

Classical physics does not reflect the difference between past and future due to its mathematical structure. This prompted Einstein to say that time is an illusion. Quantum theory as a theory of probabilistic statements does not describe events and does not show the difference between modes of time. Usually this problem is beyond the scope consideration of physics.

On the other hand, the inevitable difference between past, present and future is probably one of the most important conditions of our everyday experience. The present tense, the “now” moment, becomes an important problem for Weizsäcker. He believes that the distinction between past, present and future is the basis of all empirical science (or the condition of the possibility of experience in general), and the scientist reflects this in the title of his main work "Time and knowledge."

This basis potentially cannot be reduced to something else. Weizsäcker talks about time in quantum mechanics, presenting it in three modes: past, present and future. However, the experience of modern physics shows that in quantum mechanics time flows differently. It is rather a prototype of time, which is only subject to actualization.

As follows from the principle of superposition, different quantum states exist “simultaneously,” i.e. a quantum object initially, before updating its state, exists in all admissible states at once. When reducing the wave function from only one of them remains in the “superposed” state. Our ordinary time is closely connected with this kind of “events”, with the process of actualization of the potential.

The essence of the “arrow of time” in this understanding is that objects come into existence, “come into existence,” and it is with this process that the unidirectionality of time and its irreversibility are connected.

Quantum mechanics, the Schrödinger equation, describes the line between the level of possible existence and actual existence, or more precisely, it gives the dynamics, the probability of the

potential being realized. The potential itself is not given to us; quantum mechanics only points to it. Our knowledge is still fundamentally incomplete.

We have an apparatus that describes the classical world, that is, the actual, manifest world - this is the apparatus of classical physics, including the theory of relativity. And we have the mathematical formalism of quantum mechanics that describes becoming. Quantum mechanics takes us to the border of manifest existence and makes it clear that time has a distinct character.

When we try to observe the “being” of these quantum particles, elementary particles, it turns out that they do not “exist” in space and time. Here we need to talk about several different modes of existence. A quantum object in a state of superposition is not here and now, but exists on a different mode of existence, we can say that before space and time.

Weizsäcker is trying to formulate quantum mechanics as a single fundamental theory to which “all known physics today” can be reduced. It acts as a closed theory. The only possible change in a closed theory is a change in its fundamental provisions. This assumption is the premise that a successful physical theory satisfies very stringent conditions.

“Logical and mathematical content are just one of these conditions, and semantic consistency can be considered the strictest of them.”

Let us make a reservation that Weizsäcker further understands by semantics the physical meaning of mathematical concepts. Mathematical concepts acquire physical meaning (semantics) through the application of the way in which everyday language describes our relationship with nature.

Not surprisingly, quantum theory has generated controversy over its interpretation. It could not be combined not only with the picture of the world in classical physics, but also with various provisions that relate to metaphysics. The point is to understand and identify this discrepancy.

After this, one must decide whether this incompatibility is worth studying as an advance in philosophical science or as a flaw in the theory. Weizsäcker is based on the belief that the emphasis is on the promotion of a fundamental type in philosophy.

It was Bohr who first realized that quantum theory needed a really strong break with classical physics. For him, the attitude towards empirically confirmed and conceptually complete classical physics became a key issue, which was identified in the principle of correspondence.

Quantum theory can only be valid in some cases when it assumes classical physics as its own boundary case.

Focusing on the classical concepts of light and matter, three solutions can be proposed:

1. There are only particles.
2. There is only a field.
3. There are two of these phenomena in interaction.

Quantum mechanics has come up with an unexpected solution to the paradox. However, before such a solution was obtained (Copenhagen Interpretation), the above three solutions were tested based on this mechanics. Heisenberg proposed the principle of uncertainty of position and

momentum, and Bohr proposed the principle of wave complementarity and particles, and then they agreed on the formulation that complementarity serves as a basis for uncertainty.

In the 1958 article "Quantum Physics and Philosophy," N. Bohr writes: "Far from limiting our desire to ask questions in the form of experiments, the concept of complementarity simply characterizes the possible answers obtained as a result of such research in the case where the interaction between the measuring device and the object constitutes an inseparable part of the phenomenon."

Matter and light are neither particle nor wave. However, when trying to describe them, one has to use both representations. The reality of one representation limits the reality of the other; this is the basis of the Copenhagen interpretation.

The structure that Weizsäcker adheres to in his book *The Construction of Physics* is more abstract than Bohr's proposal, so perhaps he would not have accepted it. However, during construction, the concept of phenomenon developed by Bohr was of great importance.

We see how this concept of phenomenon embraces as a whole those elements that appeared only separately in the contending schools of positivism, realism and apriorism. We are talking about sensory perceptions of real objects that have already received a conceptual interpretation.

The introduction of time is not carried out from the very beginning as a numerical continuum, but as a result of the division of past, present, future, all of this is inherent in our experience. The concept of irreversibility is considered as the course of a certain event, which as a result of experience can turn into a phenomenon.

The difficulty that scientists have with this explanation arises from the fact that they assume a mathematical model of the event, but do not try to delve into how the terms used can make sense in relation to the phenomenon. Quantum theory is constructed in accordance with the term of certain alternatives (ur-alternatives), that is, from a formula of an abstract type, reflecting what is required for empirical knowledge.

Language is needed because science ceases to exist if we cannot express anything about our knowledge. To Einstein's statement that "God does not play dice," N. Bohr has an answer, which is that it does not matter whether he plays or not, there is only the meaning of knowing what we mean when we say that God plays dice or does not play them.

That is why N. Bohr preferred to interpret the inevitability of the use of complementary terms by the limitations of our means of expression. If we do not have words that make it possible to accurately characterize a certain phenomenon, we have to use words that describe it approximately, the scope of application of these terms will limit each other.

This limitation can be explained by the specificity of the language structure or the limitations of our means of expression. The decisive factor for the complementarity of quantum mechanics is that any real measurement must be characterized using classical concepts.

Bohr's position on this issue has not changed. After this, Einstein began to believe that QM was consistent, but insufficient. Quantum mechanics does not describe the reality of the atom, but

insufficient knowledge about such a reality, which is why it can only generate statistical type readings and not deterministic predictions.

Now Einstein expressed his aspirations for a positive result in the fact that field theory would be able to obtain particles and quantum phenomena in the form of partial solutions free from singularity. However, this difficult task was never solved.

Let us move on to the question of the semantic consistency of quantum theory. The claim that quantum theory is fundamental is confirmed by the fact that it does not contain internal contradictions (it is semantically consistent). Weizsäcker identifies four stages of semantic consistency.

Such consistency must imply that its prior awareness is consistent with the tenets of the theory. Perhaps this can only happen in a limited way.

The mathematical component of the position must be strictly defined, and the primary understanding lies in the boundless everyday language. Quantum theory must be expressed broadly as semantically consistent.

This theory is a theory of probability and prediction. Forecasts are given for possible outcomes of the results of empirical measurements. Therefore, quantum theory must imply an early awareness of what options can be solved, what measurements can be made, how this can be carried out. This is why the provision dimensions serves as a basis for the study of semantic consistency.

We will look at these four stages. At the first stage, we study the features of the ordinary use of words, in which the observer is not characterized from a quantum theoretical position and receives information using measurements in a certain object. The topic is the consistency of knowledge about this subject with the help of the ψ -function, that is, the theoretical meaning itself, which should be used in connection with the primary understanding of the theory.

At the second stage, the subject's side is divided into measuring instruments and an observer with awareness. She interprets Bohr's position in the classical understanding of this measuring device as a necessity provoked by the irreversibility of phenomena in the process of measuring actions.

In the third stage, quantum theory is applied to the measuring device. At the last stage, a test is carried out to determine whether the theory can be applied to the observer himself.

The past does not require interpretation using the ψ -function, which is subject to time. The future, on the contrary, appears before us in the form of a set of probabilities (ψ -function), the reality of this set extends to the next measurement in the form of a set of ψ -functions for the potential results of the measurement.

There is only one key consequence of quantum theory in relation to past time. Any fact from the past was previously a probable action in the future. During this period, probability could be identified using the ψ function. That is why any the factual circumstance of the past must lie in the likely possible event of the object being studied.

In addition, the relative frequency of events in the past should, on average, correspond to their probability, since this can be determined from early events. In that the value of the ψ -function between the two previous measurements (M-2, M-1) indicates what assumptions can be made by a person after the occurrence of the second event regarding the first.

Let us move on to the meaning of the observer in the Copenhagen interpretation. Weizsäcker sees the problem in understanding the physical object (system), which is contained in the premises of quantum theory: "An object is an object for the subject (observer of phenomena); the fact that the observer is part of the objective world, although fundamental to Copenhagen interpretation, but is not described meaningfully by any of the five fundamental theories.

If we dismiss this question as overly philosophical, then we are faced with the conceptual problem of representing an object. "The concept of an "isolated object" is quite approximate." Quantum theory reinforces the semantic consistency of the traditional interpretation. Interpretation does not detract from knowledge; the ψ -function is defined as it.

The decrease in the wave packet does not represent a dynamic unfolding of the ψ -function according to the Schrödinger equation. It is similar to an event in which the observer learns a certain fact. Reduction does not begin yet, as long as the interaction occurs only between the object and the measuring device, and does not occur when data is not read from the device. It represents the acquisition of knowledge in the process of such reading.

According to the Copenhagen interpretation, quantum theory determines what can be known by an observer (what he can know), but does not characterize that observer. "Even when the very knowledge of the observer in materialistic or monistic philosophy is hypothetically subordinated to physics, there still remains a logical and epistemological independence of the objectively described physical state of affairs from the knowledge of the observer; this state of affairs, in the classical sense, is present whether anyone knows it or not."

Upon becoming aware of a new experience, the observer adds a new fact to his catalog, as a result of which the probability function decreases for subsequent experiences. He cannot predict himself in a deterministic sense, just like his own experience, moods, and decisions made. He cannot play the role without contradictions knowledgeable and aware.

We have come to the complex philosophical question of consciousness. Weizsäcker notes that there are no details in quantum theory that would prevent its use in relation to consciousness: "So we make our last attempt and assume that quantum theory also holds for consciousness itself. Then this, for the first time, really turns out to be the application of quantum theory to a knower subject.

Of course, the suggestion that such an application is possible is hypothetical, but it does not contradict anything in the logical structure of abstract quantum theory." In this sense, one can criticize Weizsäcker, who admits the possibility of reduction quantum theory to aspects of consciousness.

However, we consider it inappropriate to include the phenomena of consciousness in the field of quantum mechanics. “In the last few decades, it is precisely these theories that have become widespread among some philosophers of consciousness and representatives of natural sciences, for example among physicists, who are trying to explain consciousness by appealing to processes occurring at the quantum level.

Against these theories, the two-worlds argument as presented by Passmore loses its force. From the point of view of panpsychism and epiphenomenalism, consciousness is a set of mental properties that are irreducible to physical properties. The bearers of these properties are physical objects, between which causal interactions take place.”

Back in 1924, D. Slater, H.A. Krammers and N. Bohr, when introducing the wave function, argued that it cannot be of a material nature due to its complex value. In fact, W. Heisenberg also started from this position when creating the matrix formalism of quantum mechanics in 1925.

It was this point that became the subject of discussions between Heisenberg and Einstein in 1926 in Berlin, which is described in detail in the book “Part and Whole” by Heisenberg. The central point of this discussion continued to worry Einstein for the next ten years, which resulted in the creation of the EPR paradox (Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen paradox): “either 1) the quantum mechanical description of reality is incomplete or 2) when the operators corresponding to two physical quantities do not commute, these two quantities cannot be real at the same time.”

Weizsäcker is one of the few physicists who understands a key consequence of quantum mechanics. Quantum mechanics is currently a complete, empirically proven and consistent theory. It follows from quantum theory that particles cannot have reality before the act of measurement (in Einstein’s terms). This does not mean that particles do not exist before measurement.

It follows from this that we must change the concept of “existence.” To exist does not mean to exist only in space-time, but before it. Thus, there is a transition to modal philosophy. Weizsäcker applies modality to the logic of temporary statements.

A similar position on the relationship between consciousness and matter within the framework of quantum mechanics is taken by the German philosopher and follower of Weizsäcker G.P. Duerr. In the interpretation of physical knowledge G.P. Duerr and K.F. von Weizsäcker, some general intentions can be noted: the postulation of a special interpretation of matter within the framework of quantum theory and inseparability of consciousness from matter.

At the same time, we emphasize the fundamental difference between these approaches. G.P. Duerr remains in the position of Advaita Vedanta, his approach is closer to Eastern mysticism and occultism, while Weizsäcker adheres to the Western epistemological tradition, presenting physics as what we can know about matter.

The central theme of the book by G.P. Duerr's “Matter does not exist” becomes the unity of spirit and matter. The starting point of his reasoning is a banal fact from quantum mechanics associated with the wave-particle duality of the behavior of quantum objects. Depending on how the experiment is carried out, we observe either a corpuscular picture or a wave picture.

You can take the simplest experiment, namely the double-slit experiment, and carry out the experiment in one way or another at the very last moment, namely after the quantum particles have passed through the two slits. And depending on how the experiment was carried out, we will get either a wave picture on the screen or a corpuscular one.

Such an experiment is analyzed very carefully by J. A. Wheeler and asks the question - what is the nature of a quantum particle before measurement? His answer is paradoxical; before measurement, a quantum object has neither one nor the other nature. In a certain sense it exists before measurement.

He made this conclusion in the article "Quantum and the Universe," which was published on the centenary of the birth of A. Einstein. But, generally speaking, Einstein himself came to the same conclusion in his famous work "Can we consider that the quantum mechanical description of physical reality is complete?"

Experiments conducted at the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st centuries showed the impossibility of introducing "hidden parameters", both under the assumption of local and non-local realism. There is only one option left - quantum objects are not objects "real".

Hans-Peter Dürr proceeds from this firmly established fact and argues that the observed reality depends on the observer, and here he adheres to the extreme point of view that it is all in the consciousness of the observer, and the Cartesian division into subject and object is here does not work.

At the same time, Dürr is an adherent of Indian Advaita Vedanta, in the sense that everything is one and not different from the divine: "At the core, everything is one. Our language is fragmented. Distinctions are made in language because it is not able to express at once the entire integrity of the world.

We separate the relationships so that we can then talk in more detail about the separated subject. However, the question remains what we gain through this action. If at first I separate, then I must unite it all again."

I would like to present Martin Heidegger's critique of this kind of view. It was given to them in the book "Zollikon Seminars". In this book of Heidegger, there is probably the only place where he does not speak in "esoteric" language. Almost the entire book is devoted to criticism of the method of modern natural science. Already on the first pages of the text, Heidegger outlines a range of issues, which will then be consistently outlined further.

From the very beginning, somewhere in the first three pages, Heidegger formulates two key provisions - the "non-objectification" of man and the connection between the problem of measurability and reality, where Heidegger refers to the words of Max Planck that only what can be measured is real.

The field of natural science is the field of “objectification,” according to Heidegger, that which can be “measured,” “calculated,” and “predicted.” This is the realm of causality and determinism. Man, the domain of “Dasein,” does not and cannot belong to this domain; on this basis, he criticizes Weizsäcker’s point of view and calls this approach “extremely subjectivist.”

There is another point here that Dürr touched on, namely the separation of subject and object. Heidegger also touches on this issue; he criticizes the concept of “object” and “subject” in modern science, but does not at all say that both concepts should somehow be combined.

Moreover, as a supporter of early Greek philosophy and a phenomenologist, he considers a natural object as “standing-in-itself”, and the existence of which is revealed to a person standing “in the clearing of being”, “to the existing person”, who goes beyond the boundaries of natural existence. So the frequent references of many authors that the subject-object division must be overcome with references to Heidegger are not true.

Quantum theory is currently closed, but what could be behind it? An updated closed theory that focuses on the correspondence principle of quantum theory could be the physical key to new progress in the interpretation of quantum theory. It would apply modern theory as a preliminary awareness and propose a method for studying this awareness. However, closed theories are revealed as something fundamental and revolutionary; they cannot be developed in any order.

philosophical justification for the basis of his work in more detail in the book “Time and Knowledge.” The work “Construction of Physics” contributes to this from the side of natural science knowledge, which can be carried out using the immanent analysis of quantum theory and its primary awareness. We are talking about the structure of time and the concept of alternative.

Their relationship is manifested in the fact that any alternative is associated with issues in the future, the solution of these issues is possible due to the irreversibility of measurement results, that is, due to the factual nature of the past. The ur-alternatives hypothesis could be an important step in the boundaries of quantum theory.

Its appearance is possible due to the presence of questions about the elements of the potential and the possible in quantum theory, but still this makes it possible to hope for the addition of provisions about elementary particles in the form of consequences to quantum theory and the theory of relativity. There is an assumption that only such decisive actions in the matter of interpretation can produce results.

The criteria of reality in quantum mechanics are violated in some way. Characteristic of philosophical “realism” is the fact that this direction cannot explain its centralized interpretation of reality by the method of definition, but some philosophers ignore it, while others assume it as a matter of course a matter of course.

From a formal point of view, classical physics acted in the opposite direction. She formed a definition of the existence of her phenomena using everyday things, which for mathematical description were brought to bodies that fill space and to material points. Properties such as reality

and materiality come from things. The idea of unity was adopted from the metaphysics of the Greeks.

Weizsäcker begins with the concept of time in terms of present, future and past. This structure serves as the condition of possibility of experience. "It is precisely this connection of timeless metaphysics with the general theory of relativity that is in direct opposition to the methodological starting point of this book.

Not for the sake of criticizing metaphysics, to which we will return only at the end, but for the purpose of constructing physics, we begin with time in its modes of present, past and future. We are not We affirm that this structure of time is the ultimate truth. But we maintain that it underlies all experience and therefore all experimental science."

Temporal structure represents little "subjectivity" for Weizsäcker and makes it possible to distinguish between subject and object. After this, within its boundaries we can answer what it means to interpret being as "reality." A realist defines existing phenomena as facts. Factuality is related to the past. Einstein interprets the space-time continuum, filled with events from reality, as identical to the present, past and future.

Thus, in Weizsäcker we see the Copenhagen interpretation in a consistent formulation. Knowledge depends on the information possessed by the knowing subject. Subject and object are inseparable. Knowledge is not purely subjective: it depends on objective facts.

Discontinuity exists in the description of information growth. Quantum theory describes what an observer can know. The measurement determines (not deterministically, not causally) an actually possible alternative and irreversibly produces the corresponding fact.

The latter in this case determines the probabilities for an infinite number of future events (Schrodinger equation). Requirements in relation to the past: every fact was once a possibility; the relative frequency values must match. All the "paradoxes" are based on the same error: ψ ιτσελφ is perceived as an objective fact (objective wave field).

In 1927, the Copenhagen Interpretation was formulated by Niels Bohr and Werner Heisenberg and most fully philosophically interpreted by Weizsäcker. The following points can be noted as conclusions. The reduction of the wave function according to Weizsäcker is not an objective process, but occurs in the mind of the observer, therefore the apparatus of quantum mechanics can be applied to spiritual processes. The body, in a sense, acts as a measuring instrument for consciousness.

In the Copenhagen interpretation, a special role is given to time and the concept of alternative. The alternative is associated with a possibility in the future, which occurs due to the irreversibility of measurement results and the factual nature of the past. In particular, the scientist reduces everything to the thesis that nothing can be said about matter in itself. You can think about it metaphysically.

We can only set the probability within which the phenomena of the material world are embodied. This involves a measuring instrument and an observer.

In experiment and observation, probability waves of events interfere (resonance). Only then does the probability of certain material phenomena become observable. The idea of the existence of material objects is just an illusion that is completed by the observer.

The modern concept of symmetry can be considered from two sides as a philosophical concept and a methodological principle of knowledge, therefore symmetry is very widely used. Symmetry plays a heuristic role in the construction of unified theories.

Historically, symmetry was associated with the “harmony of the world,” the conviction of which helped I. Kepler make outstanding discoveries (Kepler’s Laws). This same conviction was largely the guiding principle in the work of A. Einstein. In essence, physical theories, including modern ones, reflect the search for harmony. In this regard, the continuity of the understanding of symmetry as homogeneity, proportionality, proportionality and even some balance between the parts of the whole.

In the 20th century, the importance of symmetry in the construction of physical theories increased due to the development of the concept of physical principles of symmetry. E. Noether later established the laws between the invariance of a physical system with respect to symmetry transformations. V.A. Fock introduced non-spatial symmetry to explain random degeneracy in the hydrogen atom.

Symmetries can be divided into two types: geometric and dynamic. Internal or dynamic symmetries are widely used in modern physics. In particle physics, gauge symmetry is used, a term introduced by G. Weyl. Asymmetry is inherent in objects and phenomena, just like symmetry.

It would not be an exaggeration to say that the most interesting results in physics were achieved when the laws of symmetry breaking were clarified.

In modern physics, symmetry properties are used for classification problems, identifying new conservation laws, and constructing new generalized theories. The principle of conservation is closely related to the principle of symmetry. The universality of application of this principle can be traced back to antiquity.

The principle of conservation is the basis of a scientific theory, containing statements about the immutability, invariance of objects of study - things, properties or relationships - in the process of constructing a system of concepts in a certain field of knowledge.

In any case, when constructing a theory, Weizsäcker is already guided by these principles. Simplicity is realized in the desire to *with* a scientific program to combine general relativity, the theory of elementary particles and quantum mechanics and cosmology. He tries to find a philosophical basis for the synthesis of relativistic and quantum principles. Symmetry acts as such a beginning. Symmetry is a blessing; Plato spoke about this. It expresses order.

Physics of quantum information is a very rapidly developing field of knowledge. It arose at the intersection of quantum mechanics and computer science. At different times, this topic was

addressed by A. Zeilinger, A. Eckert, M. Nielsen, I. Chang, J. Preskill, who studied both general and specific issues of quantum information.

Eizsacker attached key importance, together with his theory of ur-alternatives, to information theory in quantum mechanics in the construction of physics. Starting from the concept of an ur-alternative, he is developing a large-scale program for constructing an integral building of a unified physical theory.

Weizsäcker's basic, fundamental theory is quantum mechanics. If we start from the concept of an ur-alternative, then the state space of quantum theory and the fundamental physical symmetries that follow from it are easily constructed.

Note that ur-alternatives and their corresponding quantum objects, which are not yet specified in abstract quantum theory, in contrast to ordinary, classically understood particles, are not localized objects in space. Moreover, the structure of space-time itself follows, as shown Weizsäcker, from the concept of ur-alternatives. Thus, a relational theory of space-time is constructed.

In quantum information theory, Weizsäcker's ur-alternative precisely corresponds to the concept of a "qubit," a dyad of states that is initially integral and indivisible. Only when measured does the qubit randomly go into one of two possible states.

Weizsäcker seeks and finds the foundations of quantum theory and builds quantum mechanics from these premises. His Ur-theory is an attempt to reconstruct and understand the structure of the world based on the concept of binary alternatives. In the course of evolution, the number of forms increases, which is why evolution for Weizsäcker is "a measure of the multiplicity of forms."

Weizsäcker's student, Holger Lihre, writes about the evolution of the cosmos as an evolution of information. "Evolution as a whole can be represented in a generalized form as the reproduction of increasingly complex structures - elementary particles, atoms, molecules, etc."

These structures can be considered as different semantic levels. One of the goals of the theory of primordial alternatives is to describe evolution as the evolution of information, where information at a higher semantic level can be explained by information at lower levels.

Ur-alternatives are at the lowest semantic level and represent a qubit. However, the theory of initial alternatives lacks a method for describing the transition from one semantic level to another. Due to the high degree of abstraction and Due to the natural science "non-canonicity", Weizsäcker's ur-theory is quite rarely covered by scientists, in contrast, for example, to Penrose's twistor program.

On the contrary, this degree of abstraction of the ur-theory aroused the praise of Klaus Mainzer, one of the world's leading experts in the field of nonlinear dynamics, the theory of self-organization of complex systems and artificial intelligence. In his work, he argues that the scientific program of ur-theory seeks to justify the significance of fundamental symmetries from fundamental assumptions (hypotheses).

This theory is also mentioned by the physicist Alfred Gierer, a specialist in the field of biophysics and the history of natural sciences, and Bernd-Olaf Küppers, a German physicist and philosopher, a specialist in the field of natural sciences, who put forward the statement, that ur-theory can tell us the amount of potential information about the universe.

Interesting philosophical statements on ur-theory are contained in biographical books about Weizsäcker by such authors as Thomas Gernitz and Michael Drieschner.

With further development of the mathematical apparatus, this theory could possibly give significant philosophical and physical results, but so far it is not technically equipped enough and there are no convincing, empirically verifiable predictions that could be confirmed or tested against other programs or the standard model.

As Holger Liehre put it: “And yet it is remarkable that Weizsäcker, connecting spinor mathematics and space-time physics, already in the fifties developed a context that today turned out to be very significant in a number of advanced programs on quantum gravity.

Perhaps the strength of this approach lies primarily in the degree of abstraction of its concepts, within the framework of which the fundamental problems of modern philosophy of physics can be explored in an appropriate way - and not simply by adapting through simplification.

Abstractness in this context acts as an advantage, an opportunity to go beyond established boundaries, as an attempt to get closer to the beginning or reconstruction of quantum mechanics. He creates his own abstract “information space”.

This figurative expression largely emphasizes Weizsäcker’s characteristic synthetic view of physics and philosophy, which in the article “Gestalt Circle and Complementarity” is formulated as follows: “The prospect opens up regarding the possibility that all laws of physics are consequences of a simple basic logical-ontological law, before which we ourselves partially guessed, at first only relying on empirical clues.

The answer to the question why physics is satisfied with matter would be: because logic is satisfied with it.

One could, on the contrary, try to say: if there are true statements about the soul with which logic is satisfied, then one could expect that physics will be equally satisfied with the soul, which, therefore, reveals its corporeality.

In philosophy, there has always been a gap between form and matter, and Weizsäcker is trying to overcome it by using the apparatus of quantum mechanics. Matter is initially opposed to form (for Aristotle). Such reflections led Weizsäcker to the bold idea that the physical description of reality can be reduced to quantum information: “From now on information for us is located at the systematic place of the numerical measure of substance.

On the other hand, we explained information as a measure of many forms. The development of physics seems to bring us back to an understanding of form as a substance in the flow of

phenomena. Are we returning to the philosophy of eidos? Our answer is both yes and no. Yes: The philosophy of eidos means the stage of abstraction, behind which the mechanical model of physics was left behind, starting from the 17th century. Abstract quantum theory forces us to return to this level of abstraction.

No: The separation of the underlying and the unchangeable means the recognition of time, flow in the form in which the philosophy of eidos sought to avoid them. We can talk about form only when we at the same time recognize the evolution of forms.”

Primary alternatives are not specific objects in time and space; their interaction and actualization gives rise, recall, to relational space-time. Of course, this suggests parallels between primary alternatives and Leibniz’s concept of the monad. You can refer to the definition: “The monad (from the Greek μονάς, gender μονάδος - unit, one; lat. monas) is an indivisible incomposite unity, measure and prototype of number.

Monad is the beginning of being, the matter of which is another, an “indefinite two,” a dyad.” Thus, we come to the point that Weizsäcker’s scientific program is oriented towards monism, which is trying to get away from the Cartesian dualism of soul and body, relying on quantum principles.

Using quantum theoretical concepts embedded in the primary alternative, Weizsäcker tried to build a “fabric” of space-time, which is not primary, but is relational in nature. At the same time, Weizsäcker, discussing the fundamental nature of quantum mechanics, raises the question of the connection between spiritual processes and quantum phenomena.

This topic is the most difficult, since our material body has a connection with consciousness, and this connection may be of a quantum nature, but this requires further research. Thus, information for Weizsäcker, if we take a bundle of form, matter and information, is a numerical measure of substance or a measure of the multiplicity of forms. For Weizsäcker, form serves as the basis of matter, and ur-alternatives act as the source material for the reconstruction of the object.

In our opinion, it should be noted that Weizsäcker’s information is closer to the concept of the revealed than to eidos (form) in Aristotle’s interpretation. This can be seen in the example of updating primary alternatives, when only one of two solutions is implemented.

Weizsäcker’s philosophical justification lacks the characteristics of the “becoming” of alternatives, which is relevant within the framework of his philosophy, since he considers the transition from the primary alternative to a decided (definite) alternative. This is one of the key points of his apparatus - the transition from a binary alternative to a specific alternative (phenomenon).

What is missing here is the concept of “actualization” of the primary alternative, the “becoming” of the revealed, associated with the ontological “gap” between the realms of the other and the revealed.

Probability is one of the key concepts in Weizsäcker’s philosophical constructs, and it is also directly related to the concept of information: “For now we adhere to the usual definition of information in terms of probability. Let a K-variant alternative to the outcome of the experiment be given, i.e., K possible mutually exclusive events x_k ($k = 1, 2 \dots K$). We expect x_k to occur if this alternative is solved with probability p_k .”

The higher the probability of an event, the more potential information it contains, and vice versa. Information appears in binary alternatives only when the quantum alternative has already been solved. Each binary alternative can take one of the mutually exclusive yes-no states. Wherever there are several different possibilities, but only one is actually realized, goes into reality, comes into being, it makes sense to talk about the information that this realized possibility carries.”

In the Copenhagen interpretation, quantum mechanics is seen as a kind of generalization of probability theory. The probability of each state is different; the entire system is described by a probability distribution. From a statistical point of view, the distribution carries all the information about the quantum system. The state vector carries all the information everything you can know about the system.

If it is expanded into the basis vectors of the operator of the measured quantity, then this superposition contains the entire amplitude of the probability of the occurrence of one or another events. How does collapse happen? Here you can turn to a comparison with dice. When throwing dice, one or another combination appears, the result goes from uncertain to definite.

The probability distribution function collapses into one specific value - the one that fell as a result. Now we describe the current state of the system not by a set of states (corresponding probabilities), but by one dropped value. It now has a 100% probability.

A similar process occurs when measuring a quantum system; its state vector from superposition collapses into one of the basis vectors corresponding to the realized alternative.

By definition, the state vector is a quantity that contains the most complete information about the system. If the observer has received information about which of the alternatives has been realized, then the state vector with which he describes the system must be updated. From this moment on, he describes the system with a new state vector, taking into account the obtained information, that is, the corresponding basis vector of the measured quantity operator, the one that corresponds to the measured eigenvalue.

The difference between the probabilistic description of dice and quantum mechanics is that in the first case we consider probability only a convenient approximation. Behind the function distribution is based on a real-life physical system - dice. In classical mechanics, if we know the initial conditions, we can trace in detail the entire dynamics of their movement at any subsequent moment in time.

In principle, we can predict which way the cubes will fall, and therefore describe in detail the process behind the collapse of the probability distribution. In quantum mechanics there is nothing behind the state vector, no more detailed description exists, there are no hidden mechanisms or parameters that would make it possible, at least in principle, to predict the result of a single measurement.

The difference between the probabilistic description of dice and quantum mechanics is that in the first case we consider probability only a convenient approximation. The fundamental difference between the description of a game of dice and the situation in quantum mechanics is that in the first case the classical concept of probability is used, while in QM the concept of probability is used, which has no analogue in the classical case.

KM uses the so-called. "probability amplitudes" described in complex-valued language function, which in a sense is the "square root" of the ordinary, classical concept of probability.

In principle, we can predict which way the cubes will fall, and therefore describe in detail the process behind the collapse of the probability distribution.

Weizsäcker connects the concept of probability with ur-alternatives: "From a philosophical point of view, the content of the program returns the ontology of classical physics to the concept of probability. The reconstruction of abstract quantum theory is based on the concept of finite or numerically infinite alternatives of possible facts.

The implementation of an alternative gives us a certain amount of information; a binary alternative gives us one bit, or let's call it "ur" for short. It can be assumed that with From an ontological point of view, information is neither consciousness nor matter.

"In the ontology of classical physics, form can be defined as a logical predicate that can approach reality: the form of a body or force, a form in space, possibly in time. In deriving a specific quantum theory of spacetime is introduced as a space of states of ur-alternatives, namely a continuum of possibilities of "yes-no" solutions, and particles and fields, in the classical form of bodies and forces, as a representation of the group of symmetries of this continuum.

Information is then the fundamental concept from which traditional concept of matter (*res extensa*). It is the formulation of the term information that requires comment here - the literal translation here will sound like "a measure of the number of forms" (Information ist das Maß einer Menge von Form), but here it is better convey "as a measure of the plurality of forms." The set will then reflect the totality.

Analyzing the concept of information, Weizsäcker comes to an interesting conclusion: "...can information play the role of a substance in fundamental physics. The difference in answers leads to a division into two points of view that are confused with each other in the traditional understanding of substance: substance is the unchangeable, and substance is the underlying.

In the second answer, information is what is constant for a given species. It is a measure of the number of essential characteristics of a given species *as* a species. It is what they should know if they already know that there is a living organism that reproduces (lower semantic level), and if they want to know what kind (which *eidōs*) of a living being "in particular" they have in front of them (upper semantic level) .

And in the first answer, the information is what must be known if they only know that atoms and molecules exist, and want to know under what conditions they generally combine into a living being and, in particular, into a living being of a given species. Here the information is what is underlying from a physical point of view."

Weizsäcker relational program.

Such a large-scale task includes two key areas. Weizsäcker substantiates the essence of quantum mechanics on the basis of the "logic of temporary statements." The starting point for the scientist in studying this area was the analysis of Boltzmann's justification for the second law of

thermodynamics and the principles of statistical mechanics. Can assert that the rationale used is inconsistent only if the concept of probability relates to future events.

In other cases, there is no inconsistency in this justification . “Based on considerations of consistency, one can then subsequently show that the facticity of the past and the openness of the future (in the form of the existence of documents of the past, but not the future) already follows from the irreversibility of events according to the second fundamental law.

However, the difference between now past and now future moments of time cannot be reconstructed from their form in accordance with the laws of nature that apply to each moment of time. Oddly enough, there is strong emotional opposition from almost all physicists to this conclusion.”

If we follow Weizsäcker's line of thought, we can conclude that evolution and thermodynamic irreversibility are obligatory statistical consequences of the same time structure. We are talking about realized facticity as well as future possibility. The structure of the theory is a set of components such as possibility, probability and modality cannot be ignored.

The above fact is directly related to our understanding of the foundations of quantum theory. This idea allows us to talk about the non-primary nature of the space-time structure.

Weizsäcker came to this conclusion in the period 1953-1954. The scientist actively discussed this with W. Heisenberg. The physics program proposed by Weizsäcker deserves a detailed analysis. In his work, he made the philosophical justification of physics a key point. The scientist made his first developments in the chosen direction back in the 30s.

It took almost two decades to build a holistic system of justification.

“In the spring of 1954, I put forward a hypothesis that can be divided into three statements based on each other. Now they could be formulated as follows:

1. The core of quantum theory is non-classical logic.
2. The application of this logic to its own statements determines the method of so-called secondary or multiple quantization.
3. The application of this method to the formally simplest possible questions - binary alternatives - provides a quantum theoretical explanation of the three-dimensionality of space and, in addition, the relativistic structure of space-time and relativistic field theory."

Weizsäcker traveled an impressive path, which can be schematically represented as a circle. Namely, the scientist's life path is a vivid example of the implementation of a philosophical method called “walking in circles.” The beginning of each new revolution represents a solution to the same problem, only at a higher level.

The conclusions formulated above were the result of an in-depth analysis of Heisenberg's work dating back to the period 1936-1938. These works include coverage of the problem concerning the shortest length considered within the framework of quantum theory.

The information presented in these works prompted Weizsäcker to consider the idea of studying geometry within the microworld: “In subsequent years, I devoted some time to the question of whether the smallest length of mathematical changes in geometry in the microworld might not

require the same way as they turned out to be necessary for general relativity, a change in geometry in the macrocosm and for quantum theory transition to non-commutative algebra (1951).

At the same time, the idea arose to subordinate the very geometry of the infinitely small to quantum theory. physical space. For example, shouldn't the question of whether two observed points in space are identical or different represent a quantum theoretical alternative, the resolution of which could only be predicted with some probability?

It is worth noting that it is at this stage that the idea based on the non-primacy of space originates. It should be noted that Weizsäcker takes this from abstract QM, as it was presented by von Neumann, which in its formulation does not require the concept of space-time. If you follow it, then space obeys existing quantum mechanical laws.

This was precisely the first conclusion made by the scientist. The second significant finding was the distinguishability of two points in space. The question raised can be classified as fundamental. It can be examined in detail both from classical mechanics and from the theory of relativity and quantum mechanics. In the passage above, Weizsäcker covers it only from the side of quantum mechanics.

If we analyze the question concerning the distinguishability of two points in space, then it is automatically necessary to note that it is this question that ultimately leads Weizsäcker to the concept of relational space.

The Heisenberg uncertainty principle allows us to understand the high level of complexity in answering the question posed. Also, the issue of a quantum alternative should not be overlooked. It lies in the possibility or impossibility of distinguishing between two spatial points. In this case, it will again be necessary to resort to a certain empirical procedure.

If we do not take quantum physics into account, then we can say that work on the distinguishability of two points in space became for Weizsäcker the way to define relational space. Let us consider in more detail the logic of the scientist's reasoning on this matter. First of all, it concerns the historical and philosophical roots of the problem.

Naturally, this is done from the point of view of physics. The first conclusions of work in this direction boiled down to the fact that "the absolutist and relativistic understanding of motion. Towards the absolutist tradition, among others, one can classify Ptolemy, Copernicus, Kepler, Galileo, Newton, as relativistic - Cusanus, Bellarmine, Leibniz, Mach.

Einstein's intention was relativistic, his result contained elements of absolutist understanding. The question, first of all, is what is the vocabulary with the help of which the decision in this dispute was made."

The pre-existing dispute between the geocentric and heliocentric models, dating back to the times of Claudius Ptolemy, was based on naive assumptions that a complete understanding of such concepts as "rest" and "motion" was known for certain.

That is why this dispute was called naive-intra-absolutist. But the belief gradually changed. “Nicholas Kuzansky (Kuzanets) emerged from this state of naivety around 1450. He considered the world to be infinite. Then in the very image of the world there did not exist (as it had previously been in the image of crystal spheres and a central body at rest) the criterion of rest and movement.

Consequently, motion, by definition, turns out to be only the motion of bodies relative to each other. In 1615, Cardinal Bellarmine understood this. He allowed Galileo to present the Copernican system as a mathematical hypothesis, but not as truth. “Hypothesis” in this case does not mean “assumption”, but “attribution”; By using the word “model” we come closer to the mode of expression that Bellarmine desired.

Bellarmino may have been pondering the idea of the relativity of motion for a long time. The same movements could optionally be described as geocentric or heliocentric.”

The broad issues that accompany the controversy between the geo- and heliocentric models have nevertheless reached the center of relativistic argumentation. It contains evidence that the centuries-old dispute between these two systems is simply meaningless.

Imagining the world as a finite ball, we can assume that the movement inside it is "true". However, the theory of an infinite universe demonstrates the inconsistency of this argument. In his work, Weizsäcker notes an interesting fact. The relational paradigm was not recognized as victorious even after understanding the infinity of the existing world. The proposed “kinematic description” has a generally accepted form.

The Copernican model brought only the “reasonable” into dynamics. It's about simplicity of form. Then the logical question follows: what is the substance that fills this way of thinking at the moment?

For Weizsäcker, the ontological aspect of the existing confrontation became paramount. He specified that by this aspect he means the relationships that exist and arise between matter and space. Weizsäcker pays close attention to the importance of distinguishing between the monistic and dualistic paradigms. Newton's position, which is absolute in nature, belongs to the dualistic worldview.

If you follow his line of thought, then the statement about the existence of absolute space in which bodies exist is true. The relational paradigm implies a monistic model. According to this theory, only bodies exist. Wherein spatial relationships are a consequence of their extension. The direction of Einstein's thoughts followed Mach's conclusions. She gravitates towards the monistic paradigm.

“More philosophically educated than his opponent, Leibniz thought in terms of the relationship of substance and attribute, or, logically speaking, the relationship of subject and predicate. This is the dualism that neither a physicist nor a logician can ever get rid of. Logically (in modern language), a class is a predicate and should be distinguished from its elements as subjects to which this predicate is inherent...

In physics, in addition, one can distinguish between essential predicates and contingent predicates.

Essential predicates characterize a physical object (the logical subject of statements). For example, in classical mechanics, a material point is an object that has mass, location and momentum and nothing else as attributes.

Moreover, the value of mass is an essential predicate of the corresponding individual material point; the concept “mass” is an essential predicate concept of “material point”. The essential predicate of a concept is a class of contingent predicates, just as mass is a class of possible values of mass.

Similarly, for each material point, location as an essential predicate turns out to be the class of its possible values; a material point is “an object that has a certain location.” The same applies to impulse. Quantum The theory once again divides the attributes of an object into two different basic classes: observables and states.”

Leibniz came to the conclusion that space is an essential predicate of body. In this case, the existing bodies are in a relative position. Based on this statement, we can conclude that the inevitable dualism between bodies, as well as the characteristics distance and direction, are already included in the dualism that implies substance and attribute.

Leibniz in his conclusions came to the conclusion that the dualism of the substances of body and space, considered from a philosophical point of view, is simply an optional element that has no logical basis.

Newton in his writings does not apply the concept of “substance” in relation to space. But, if we analyze his works from a logical point of view, then space and time are interpreted in them as substance or essence.

Leibniz called for understanding the concept of “space” as a set of relations that exist and arise between bodies, while the physical meaning invested in the concept of “relativity” is key in this dispute.

Leibniz supported his words in favor of relativity with a solid basis. The arguments he gave in his letters to Clark were that the actual world was completely identical to the world that was shifted ten miles to the right. At the same time, Clark objected to him, justifying his point of view with Newton’s proof of the existence of absolute space.

As a result, he argued that these two worlds have objective differences that make them non-identical. Leibniz continued to insist, relying on the principle of sufficient reason, which boiled down to the logical question: why God should have created the world here rather than there. At the same time, he argued that God does not act chaotically, but is guided by serious reasons.

“In modern terms: With respect to the group of transformations of Euclidean space, there is no geometric difference between the two locations. And *the relativity of uniform rectilinear motion* was already known to Galileo. On a uniformly floating ship, mechanics, in particular the law of free fall, have the same form as on the earth at rest.

Newton came to a solution not with philosophical, but with mathematical-empirical arguments. Newton saw that his law of motion was not mathematically allows for *the relativity of accelerated motion* , and he confirmed this empirically using a vessel experiment.

In our century, the position on the relativity of uniform motion acquired its final form in Einstein's special theory of relativity, and the problem of accelerated motion was formulated anew by him in the general theory of relativity.”

Understanding special relativity includes Euclidean geometry and classical mechanics and their relationship. Thus, Weizsäcker emphasizes: “...physical axiomatics lays the Helmholtz-Dingler operations with rigid bodies at the basis of Euclidean geometry.

It justifies the six-parameter Euclidean group of three-dimensional real rotations and translations. Classical mechanics, as it turned out by the end of the 19th century. when posing the question from the point of view of group theory (L. Lange), adds to the Euclidean group a four-parameter extension consisting of transformations that contain time.

The one-parameter subgroup of time shifts, which expresses the homogeneity of time, was most often easily perceived as a formulation of the assumption that the same laws of nature always apply. In contrast, “Galileo's transformations themselves,” which transformed inertial systems from one to another, contained a special principle of relativity, which gave rise to many philosophical discussions.”

Next, Weizsäcker again raises the topic of the difference between space and time. “Contrary to the often quoted but inaccurate expression of Minkowski, it should be noted that the special theory of relativity does not abolish the difference between space and time at all.

Points of space that do not exist objectively and moments of time that also do not exist objectively are combined (according to the special theory of relativity) into objectively existing “events” that fill the four-dimensional space-time continuum.

However, due to the indefinite nature of the Minkowski metric for the space-time continuum, it is impossible to transform time-like straight lines (and therefore possible trajectories of inertial motion) into space-like straight lines and vice versa.

It is also impossible to convert a positive light cone into a negative one using a continuous transformation; i.e., the difference between past and future also turns out to be invariant under Lorentz transformations.”

As mentioned above, space is not of a primary, absolute nature, but time is allocated. However, it has some structure. The distinction *between past , present and future* is not at all *subjective* , as most physicists believe, but reflects its essential nature.

The structure of time is closely connected with the process of formation of existence, the actualization of one of the possible states of the quantum primary alternative (Uralternative), from which, as shown Weizsäcker, it is possible to obtain the structure of space-time. Introducing the

concept of possibility, Weizsäcker raises the question of justifying the complex value of primary alternatives.

He tries to give an answer from the point of view of theoretical physics, but the justification program complex meaning was not realized by him. This is due to Weizsäcker's expanded concept of the unity of quantum mechanics.

He notes: "My current understanding of the philosophical problem of physical geometry (1974) includes the expectation that the theory of first alternatives will indeed allow one to derive the mathematical structure of the space-time continuum from quantum theory.

It overturns the traditional understanding, according to which the space-time structure does not depend on quantum theory and is already given for it. In order to be able to begin to address this issue at all, it was necessary to understand the degree of generality of quantum theory.

From this came the "attempt to understand quantum theory," which resulted in the appearance the three works mentioned here. The actual implementation of this attempt was initiated within the framework of a seminar in the winter of 1953-54, in which not only Scheibe and Sussmann took part, but, according to my recollections, also Heisenberg and Mittelstedt, and in which we discussed "an attempt to change quantum theory."

Weizsäcker lacks a justification for comprehensiveness for a holistic description of reality. In quantum mechanics we are dealing with complex-valued potential (or unobservable) and observable reality. Complexity, on the contrary, takes us to the question of whether the wave function describes a normal state or something else.

"In the standard formalism of quantum mechanics, the transition from one state to another is described using the so-called "wave function reduction" - this is a certain break, a leap in the QM formalism, which itself is not fundamentally described in any way. The attempts of many physicists to describe this phenomenon look extremely ridiculous and naive. This is inherent in the essence of things, it is with it, with this leap, that the "ungraspable" time is connected."

Weizsäcker's quantum theory of ur-alternatives is an attempt to show the universality of quantum theory, its resistance to any attempts to change. The ontological basis of the theory is the structure of time and the concept of alternative.

It is assumed that all this is the result of abstract quantum theory, which thus plays a much more important role in the characterization of physical reality than appears in classical physics. To derive concrete physics from abstract quantum theory,

Weizsäcker used the logical possibility of representing any state in a finite-dimensional abstract Hilbert space, to which a quantum-theoretical alternative corresponds, as a tensor product of a two-dimensional state.

Such two-dimensional states correspond to the quantum theoretical formulation

the simplest logical alternative, namely a binary alternative, that is, a yes-no decision. Such a binary alternative, formulated in quantum theory, must be the fundamental concept on which the description of physical reality is based, and in this role Weizsäcker calls it the original alternative.

By using the purely logical concept of alternative at a fundamental level, abstract information becomes the fundamental essence of nature. This in turn causes nature to seem to dissolve at a basic level into something purely spiritual in the sense of objective spirit.

Weizsäcker was convinced by Heisenberg that the most important philosophical event of the 20th century, the emergence of the theory of relativity and quantum theory, must be understood philosophically. From Heisenberg's later remarks on Weizsäcker's approach to the original alternatives, it becomes clear how closely physics and philosophy are related to each other in Weizsäcker's thinking: "So you would like," I interjected, "to arrange the elementary particles, and with them ultimately the world, from alternatives in the same way as Plato wanted to build his regular volumetric bodies and thereby the world from triangles.

Alternatives are as immaterial as the triangles in Plato's *Timaeus*. But if we proceed from the logic of quantum theory, then the alternative will be the fundamental form from which other, more complex forms arise through repetition.

If I understand you correctly, the path here leads from the alternative to the symmetric group, i.e. to a specific property; representatives of one or many properties are mathematical forms that reflect elementary particles, they are, so to speak, ideas of elementary particles, which ultimately correspond to a material particle as an object.

This universal design makes sense to me. Moreover, the alternative is a much more fundamental structure of our thought than a triangle. But the mathematically precise implementation of your program seems extremely difficult. For it requires such a high abstraction of thought, which has never been achieved before, at least in physics. I obviously wouldn't be able to do it."

Weizsäcker attempts to solve the fundamental problems of quantum mechanics, as consistently as possible to solve special problems. However, his program for building physics remained unfinished. The prerequisites for unified physics are laid down in quantum mechanics.

The temporal structure is the basis of physics as an experimental science. Initially, the very structure of the concept of "experience" contains a fundamental difference between the past and the future or a specific structure of time. Weizsäcker pays special attention to the structure of time, realized in three modes. The present, Weizsäcker emphasizes, is not fully taken into account in classical physics; the moment "now" is assigned a subjective meaning.

The future appears in the modal category of the possible, and we can have documented facts about the past. According to Weizsäcker, a unified physical theory can be built on temporal logic, which in turn follows from facts arising not only when immersed in narrower problems of justification of statistical physics and thermodynamics, as well as from general philosophical problems, the possibility of theory and experiment.

Temporal structure acts as a condition of possibility of experience. The systematic construction of physics requires, first of all, that a complete logic of temporal statements and only then was the physical theory based on it. Temporal statements are the basis of such logic.

Using temporal logic, one can obtain formalized judgments about the future. And the future itself is formulated using the categories “possibility” and “probability”. For the functioning of quantum logic, the mathematical apparatus of quantum mechanics is used, through which the operators $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ take the values “no” or “yes”. We also emphasize that the Weizsäcker program does not make the transition from probability to probability amplitude. Logical level in physical theory is associated with a certain ontology.

The claim that quantum theory is fundamental is confirmed by the fact that it does not contain internal contradictions (it is semantically consistent). At the same time, it is shown that semantics does not take on a completely traditional meaning in Weizsäcker, but reflects the physical meaning of mathematical concepts.

The study introduced the concept of ur-alternative. This is one of the key points of the Weizsäcker apparatus - the transition from a binary alternative to a specific alternative (phenomenon).

Weizsäcker's approach in his work was supplemented by the concept of “actualization” of the primary alternative, the “becoming” of the revealed, which is associated with the ontological “gap” between the areas of the other and the revealed.

Weizsäcker does not make a metaphysical distinction between the other (the field of complex-valued numbers) and the occurred facts of the revealed (phenomena). The visible world (the manifest and the phenomenal) is conditioned by the transcendental world, which is significantly different from the manifest. Becoming turns out to be a process that occurs in space and time.

At the same time, Weizsäcker, discussing the fundamental nature of quantum mechanics, raises the question of the connection between spiritual processes and quantum phenomena. This topic is the most difficult. We adhere to the position that in quantum mechanics the question of the relationship between spirit and matter is not addressed, but is only about the description of material existence.

The relational aspect of theory building is substantiated and introduced. Based on the temporal logic and semantic consistency of quantum theory, Weizsäcker builds his relational program. He had the idea to subordinate the very geometry of infinitely small physical space to quantum theory.

The question of the distinguishability of two points ultimately leads Weizsäcker to the concept of relational space. The tendency of the relational paradigm is monistic.

Specific consequences for the construction of a unified physics follow from the relational paradigm. If space-time is of a secondary, relational nature, then there is no point in quantizing it or building a quantum theory of gravity, Weizsäcker focuses his attention on this. Gravity in this approach is already a consequence of quantum phenomena.

Thus, we highlight three main aspects of theory building, namely transcendental, temporal and relational, which are closely interrelated. These aspects constitute a single monistic picture of the world. Based on these aspects, the ontological and epistemological universality of constructing a unified physical theory was shown.

At the same time, the epistemological and ontological settings of the theory are consistently consistent with each other. Metaphysical attitudes turn out to be irremovable from the structure of physical theory. The construction of a unified physical theory within the framework of a relational worldview, which is directly related to the monistic paradigm, turns out to be quite promising both in the physical and philosophical sense.